

Structures and Physical Properties of Polyethylene/Boron Nitride Composites by Reactive Extrusion

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ABSTRACT

High-density polyethylene (HDPE) composites with modified boron nitride (mBN) fillers, functionalized with an organosilane, were fabricated through conventional melt-extrusion processing techniques. The properties and performances of these composites were compared with those of the composites containing pristine BN and boron carbide (B₄C) fillers. The silane functionalization of the BN fillers strongly improved the interfacial adhesion between the polymer matrix and the filler. As a result, the HDPE/mBN composites showed a better dispersion state of the filler particles, larger tensile modulus, greater effective thermal conductivity, and better neutron shielding property compared with the HDPE/BN and HDPE/B₄C composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

The nuclear power generation is clean with a low cost compared with other systems based on fossil fuels. However, radiation leakage from nuclear power stations leads a huge casualties and financial and environmental damages [1–3]. Thus, recently, a lot of researchers in the field of nuclear energy have largely focused on the safety and environment issues [4]. The radiation shielding materials have been cement-based compounds containing concretes and heavy concrete, with or without lead. These cement compounds shield nuclear radiations mainly through moderating neutrons and blocking their pathways. The heavy weight and large volume of the matters, however, burden transportation in the course of construction. Moreover, the difficulty in reintegration of shielding materials after being destroyed is a critical problem [4–7].

In order To overcome these shortcomings, several polymer composites with ¹⁰B were proposed as alternative nuclear radiation shielding materials. These polymer/¹⁰B composites are not only efficient radiation shield but also are safe and convenient in construction, operation, dismantlement, and reintegration [8–11]. Among polymers used to make the composites, polyethylene (PE), possessing a high content of hydrogen atoms, plays as a mighty polymeric neutron moderator through its large scattering power. Meanwhile, it was reported that ¹⁰B-containing matters such as boron carbide (B₄C) and boron nitride (BN) are excellent neutron absorbers by virtue of their huge thermal neutron absorbances [4]. Grulke et al. fabricated high-density PE (HDPE)/B₄C composites via conventional polymer processing techniques and reported higher radiation shielding performance and better mechanical properties than the neat HDPE [8]. The HDPE/BN composites were also reported for the radiation shielding application. However, the BN fillers used in these composites suffered from the lack of interfacial adhesion with the HDPE matrix, leading to a limited improvement or even decay of physical and radiation shielding properties of the HDPE/BN composites [9]. Other polymers such as low-density PE (LDPE), epoxy, polystyrene, polyimide, and poly(4-methyl-1-pentene) were also considered as the nuclear protective matrices [8,9,12–15]. As a recent approach of enhancing the nuclear radiation shielding performance in the composite system, in 2013, Huang et al. suggested a

“Sandwich” type of neutron shielding composites with the B₄C reinforced by carbon fiber. The carbon fiber-reinforced B₄C-based neutron shielding composites enhanced not only thermal neutron shielding performance but also mechanical and thermal stabilities. Those were attributed to the appropriate combination of the B₄C with good radiation shielding property and the carbon fiber with good tensile strength and thermal conductivity [4].

In this study, HDPE composites with chemically treated BN (mBN) fillers, functionalized with an organosilane, were fabricated through conventional melt-extrusion processing techniques and their properties were compared with those of the pristine BN and B₄C composites. The surface treatment of the BN fillers strongly improved the interfacial adhesion between HDPE and BN. The enhancement of interfacial adhesion improved the dispersion state of filler, the mechanical and thermal properties, and the neutron radiation shielding property.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1. Materials

HDPE (SEETEC PM360) was provided from LG Chemical Co. of Korea. The BN (hexagonal BN, Boronid, thermal conductivity (in bulk): 50 W/mK) and B₄C (3000F, thermal conductivity: 40 W/mK) fillers with the average particle size in the range of 0.5–1.0 μm were purchased from Ceradyne, Inc. (CA, USA). 3-Aminopropyltriethoxysilane, a silane coupling agent, was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Isopropyl alcohol and stearic acid with research grade were supplied from Daejung Chemicals & Metals in Korea.

2.2. Surface chemical treatment of BN

To improve the interfacial adhesion between the HDPE matrix and the BN filler, a surface treatment of the filler was carried out. To a 5-L glass reactor equipped with a condenser, BN particles and isopropyl alcohol were added and the mixture was vigorously agitated at 70 °C for 30 min. Then, 3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane (6% by weight of BN) was introduced to the reactor to start silylation reaction for the surface treatment of BN. Figure 1 shows a schematic representation of the surface treatment of BN using the triethoxysilane. The reaction was conducted at 70 °C for 4 h. Finally, the resulting slurry was filtered off and dried under vacuum at 70 °C for 8 h to obtain mBN filler.

2.3. Preparation of HDPE composites

HDPE/BN, HDPE/mBN, and HDPE/B₄C composites were fabricated using a twin screw extruder (L/D: 40, Bautek Co., Korea). The extrusion process was conducted at 180 °C and was repeated 3 times to improve the dispersivity of filler particles in the HDPE matrix. Stearic acid was used as a lubricant in the compounding process.

2.4. Characterization

The surface functionalization of BN was examined using a Fourier transform infrared spectrometer instrument (FT-IR, Spectrum GX FTIR spectrometer, PerkinElmer Inc.). A field emission scanning electron microscope (FE-SEM, S-4200, Hitachi) was used to observe the fracture surface morphology of HDPE/BN, HDPE/mBN, and HDPE/B₄C composites. For examination of the neutron shielding function of the HDPE composites, equipment from Korea Atomic Energy Research Institute (KAERI) in Daejeon, Korea was utilized. Figure 2 displays a real picture of the equipment and a drawing. The neutron source was ²⁵²Cf of 2.1 MeV, which was moderated via passing through a HDPE plate (thickness of 5 cm) to assess the radiation shielding characteristic of HDPE composites focusing on the attenuation of low energy neutrons. The shadow cone excludes the scattered neutrons through atmosphere and indoor. The distance between the ²⁵²Cf neutron source and the specimen was 10 cm and the distance between the neutron source and the detector was 100 cm. The specimens with dimensions of 20 cm × 20 cm and 2 cm in thickness were prepared via hot pressing the composites at 180 °C and 12 MPa for 10 min. Tensile examinations were carried out using an Instron 5560 system according to ASTM D638. The rate of elongation was 50 mm min⁻¹ and the measurement was repeated 5 times per specimen. For determining effective thermal conductivity, first, thermal diffusivity and specific heat capacity values were measured using a Netzsch LFA-447 Nanoflash System with pyroceramic references. Then, the effective thermal conductivity, κ , was calculated from the equation of $\kappa = T_d \times d \times C_p$, where T_d , d , and C_p are thermal diffusivity (mm² s⁻¹), density (g cm⁻³), and specific heat capacity (J kg⁻¹ K⁻¹), respectively. The bulk density, d , was determined using the

weight and volume of a composite specimen with dimensions of 10 mm × 10 mm × 2 mm. The average bulk density obtained from five measurements was used to minimize errors in the effective thermal conductivity experiment.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Surface characterization

First, BN particles were surface-functionalized with a 3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane to improve the adhesion between HDPE matrix and BN particles. This expectation is based on the affinity between the C–C bonds in HDPE and the C–C bonds in the silane moieties chemically attached to the surface of BN, as shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Schematic representation for the surface modification of BN with a trialkoxysilane.

The structural analysis of the silane-treated BN was performed with FT-IR technique; the results are shown in Fig. 2. The two peaks at 763 and 1,285 cm^{-1} are assigned to B–N bond [9]. After chemical treatment with organosilane, however, two peaks appeared at 1031 and 1123 cm^{-1} , assigned to the Si–O–Si and Si–O–CH₂–CH₃ moieties, respectively [16]. One small peak at 3000 cm^{-1} is assigned to the aliphatic C–H stretching, which is originated from the organosilane grafted onto the BN surface. Appearance of the newly developed three peaks indicates that the silane functionalization of BN was successfully done.

Figure 2: FT-IR spectra of BN and mBN.

3.2. Morphology observations

The surface treatment of BN affected the morphology of HDPE/BN composites. Figure 3 shows SEM micrographs of the fracture surfaces of HDPE/BN, HDPE/mBN, and HDPE/B₄C composites. In HDPE/BN composites, many agglomerated pristine BN particles were observed with a broad size-distribution ranging from 1 to 8 μm . A plenty of interfacial voids, which could be formed during fracture, were observed at the interface between the HDPE and BN. On the other hand, the SEM micrograph of the composite containing mBN exhibited a good dispersion of particles in the matrix with a small particle size and narrow size distribution of 1–4 μm and few interfacial voids. The smaller size of mBN particles and the less interfacial voids at the interfaces between HDPE matrix and mBN particles indicate that mBN has a better interfacial affinity to HDPE matrix than pristine BN. The fracture feature of HDPE/mBN composites was close to that of HDPE/B₄C composites rather than to HDPE/BN.

Figure 3: SEM micrographs of the fractured surface of HDPE/BN, HDPE/mBN, and HDPE/B₄C composites: (a) BN (20 phr), (b) mBN (20 phr), (c) B₄C (20 phr), (d) a magnified image of (a), (e) a magnified image of (b), and (f) mBN (100 phr).

3.3. Mechanical properties

Figure 4 shows the tensile moduli of HDPE/BN, HDPE/mBN, and HDPE/B₄C composites with various filler contents. The neat HDPE indicated a tensile modulus of 361 MPa. All the inorganic fillers used in this study obviously raised the modulus of the HDPE matrix and the modulus value increased as the filler content increased. The moduli of the HDPE/BN and HDPE/mBN composites regardless of surface treatment of BN were greater than those of the HDPE/B₄C composites. The HDPE/mBN composite revealed higher tensile modulus than HDPE/BN composite, due to the effect of the surface treatment, especially at high loading of 100 phr. The tensile modulus of HDPE composite with 100 phr of mBN was 1,091 MPa, which is 3 times larger than that of the pristine HDPE and 23% larger than that of the HDPE/BN.

Figure 4: Tensile modulus versus filler content for HDPE/BN, HDPE/mBN, and HDPE/B₄C composites. The measurement was repeated 5 times per each sample and averaged.

3.4. Effective thermal conductivity

Figure 5 shows the effective thermal conductivities of HDPE/BN, HDPE/mBN, and HDPE/B₄C composites. Thermal conductivity of the nuclear radiation shielding materials is quite important issue, because the thermal conductive materials are helpful of releasing the heat generated from nuclear reactors [4,10]. The neat HDPE had an effective thermal conductivity of $0.50 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$. The addition of BN, mBN, and B₄C fillers increased the effective thermal conductivity, featuring upward lines with increasing filler content. HDPE/BN and HDPE/mBN showed much higher effective thermal conductivities than HDPE/B₄C, and the HDPE/mBN revealed a little larger effective thermal conductivity than HDPE/BN. Thermal conductivity of polymeric composites is mainly governed by the type and content of particulate fillers. For a large increase in thermal conductivity, 50–60 vol % of fillers should be incorporated in the composites [13,17,18]. In this work, the maximum volume content of fillers was around 31 vol % much less than percolation concentration ($\rho_{\text{HDPE}}=0.95$, $\rho_{\text{BN}}=2.1$, $\phi_{\text{BN}}=0.31$ at 100 phr). Therefore, the effective thermal conductivities of the composites were still small ($< 1.3 \text{ W/mK}$). Nevertheless, in this work, BN-incorporated composites showed larger effective thermal conductivity than B₄C-incorporated ones at the same filler content. The surface functionalization of BN filler led to a meaningful improvement of the effective thermal conductivity of composites. The surface modification of fillers is attributed to an alleviated phonon scattering at the interface of HDPE matrix and mBN particle, compared with that of the HDPE/BN composites. In most cases, the phonon scattering at the interface of matrix/filler restricts heat transfer and a poor interfacial adhesion between the matrix and the filler leads to a large phonon scattering [12]. The enhancement of tensile modulus and effective thermal conductivity in the HDPE/mBN composites is strongly attributed to the improved interfacial affinity between the HDPE and mBN filler.

Figure 5: Effective thermal conductivity versus filler content for HDPE/BN, HDPE/mBN, and HDPE/B₄C composites. The measurement was repeated 5 times per each sample and averaged.

3.5. Neutron shielding

Finally, the neutron shielding characteristics of HDPE/BN, HDPE/mBN, and HDPE/B₄C composites at various filler contents (0–200 phr) were determined (Fig. 6). Neutron transmission factor, I/I_0 was measured to assess the neutron shielding abilities, where I_0 and I are the intensity of incident neutron beam and the intensity of neutron beam transmitted through the thickness direction of the specimen, respectively. The sample thickness was fixed at 2 cm. The neat HDPE revealed I/I_0 value of 0.765. The incorporation of B₄C filler into HDPE decreased the transmission factor, as already reported in the literature [8], and the value reached to 0.715 at 100 phr of B₄C. Unexpectedly, the I/I_0 value of HDPE/BN composites increased with an increase in BN content, which was observed as 0.793 at 100 phr of BN. In the case of HDPE/mBN composite, the I/I_0 value rapidly decreased with an increase in mBN content. The HDPE/mBN composite prepared in this study surprisingly revealed the attenuation ability of neutron surpassing the HDPE/B₄C composites in the whole range of filler content. Especially the HDPE/mBN composite with a filler content of 100 phr indicated I/I_0 value of 0.687. The HDPE/BN composites exhibited less radiation shielding efficiency than HDPE/B₄C composite. Moreover, an increase in BN concentration in the HDPE matrix deteriorated the neutron shielding performance, due to a very weak interfacial adhesion between the HDPE and the pristine BN. The surface functionalization of BN strengthened the interfacial adhesion between HDPE matrix and BN particles and dramatically enhanced the neutron shielding ability. As a result, for the preparation of high-performance radiation shielding composite materials, not only an excellent shielding property of each component (matrix and filler) is necessary but also an appropriate interfacial property control with a better compatibility between the components should be carefully considered.

Figure 6: Neutron transmission factor versus filler content for HDPE/BN, HDPE/mBN, and HDPE/B₄C composites.

4 CONCLUSION

HDPE/silane-treated mBN composites were fabricated through conventional melt-extrusion and their composites were compared with properties of the composites with pristine BN and B₄C fillers. The silane functionalization of the BN fillers strongly improved the interfacial adhesion between HDPE and mBN and provided fine dispersion of mBN fillers in the matrix. As a result, the HDPE/mBN composite showed better dispersion state of fillers, higher tensile modulus, higher effective thermal conductivity, and superior neutron shielding property than HDPE/BN and HDPE/B₄C composites. This work demonstrates that for the preparation of high-performance radiation-shielding composite materials, an appropriate interfacial adhesion property between polymer and fillers is crucial and should be carefully controlled.

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